

**APAMARGA KSHAR SUTRA BANDHANA AND APAMARGA KSHAR NADI VRANA
BASTI IN BHAGANDARA (FISTULA -IN-ANO)****Dr. Shrikant Patel^{1*}, Dr. Deepak Kulshretha², Dr. O. P. Diwedi³**¹Principal, Faculty of Ayurveda, MGU, Sehore.²Principal, Govt. Auto. Ayurveda College, Rewa.³Professor, Dept. of Rachana Sharir, Govt. Auto. Ayurveda College, Rewa.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Shrikant Patel**

Principal, Faculty of Ayurveda, MGU, Sehore.

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INTRODUCTION

Bhagandara is one of the recurring diseases occurring in ano-rectal region which is difficult to treat because of its high recurrence rates. In Ayurveda, Bhagandara has been mentioned as one among Ashtamaharoga, it is characterized by the formation of a pidika near the anus that ruptures, leading to a persistent, painful, and often recurrent tract with pus discharge. It attributed to imbalances in Vata and Pitta doshas, leading to tissue disruption, inflammation, and infection. It involves disruption of Rakta and Mamsa and the formation of Aama which contributes to chronic infection. Acharya Sushruta mentioned five types of Bhagandara. He had explained Shastra Karma along with Kshara karma and Bhesaja Chikitsa for treatment. Acharya Sushruta has explained Nidana, Samprapti, Bheda, Lakhshana, Upadrava and Chikitsa in detail. The disease which creates Darana in the area of pelvis, rectum & urinary bladder is called as Bhagandara and when these are not opened it's called as Bhagandara Pidaka. An abnormal passage between a hollow or tubular organ (Bhaga, Guda, or Basti) and the body surface or between two hollow or tubular organs is called fistula. Fistula in ano, is an abnormal tubular structure connecting the anal canal to the skin around the anus, most commonly caused by an infection from an anal gland or perianal abscess. Symptoms include pain, drainage of pus or blood, and skin irritation. Prolong sitting, unhygienic condition, obesity, repeated irritation due to hair may increase the risk of occurrence. Treatment for an anal fistula is surgical, with options like fistulotomy. Kshara destroys the vitiated tissue and make them fall off. It is the most important among Shastra and Anushastra because it does functions like excision, cutting and scrapping, also mitigates all the three Doshas. Acharya Sushruta described that Nadivrana (sinus) should be cut open by Kshara Sutra and, he said the same procedure should be adopted for Bhagandara. Kshara application in the form of Ksharasutra, in anorectal diseases has become more popular due to its easy approach and low rate of recurrence. Ksharasutra induces both mechanical and chemical cutting and healing. Direct reference of Ksharasutra is found in Sushruta for treatment of Nadivrana. Chakradatta has referred to a medicated thread coated with Snuhi and Haridra powder in treatment of Arsha and Bhagandara. But the modified Ksharasutra available now a day is re-established by the Dept. of Shalya Tantra, Banaras Hindu University. The standard Ksharasutra is prepared by 11 coatings of Snuhi Ksheera then 7 coatings of Snuhi Ksheera and Apamarga Kshara and then again 3 coatings of Snuhi Ksheera and Haridra Churna.

CASE REPORT

Patient Name- xxxx, Age- 55-year, Gender- male Occupation- Businessman

Date of admission- 06/1/2025 Date of recovery-10/2/2025

Chief complaints and duration

Patient complains of mild pus discharge with pain at the right side of perianal region in the last 6 months.

H/o present illness

Patient was apparently normal before 8 months. Then he had developed boil which started mild discharge in between in perianal region since last 7 months. He also complained of pain and discomfort while sitting. He had taken analgesics without prescription for it, but didn't get any relief.

Therefore, for further treatment he came to OPD of Shalyatanra, Global Ayurvedic Hospital, MGU, Sehore.

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Family history

No H/O HTN, DM or any other major illness General examination G.C-moderate, afebrile CVS- S1 S2 Normal. Pulse- 84/min, BP- 120/85 mm Hg, RS- Chest clears on both sides.

Digestive System- Appetite- normal, Bowel- constipated. Uro-genital System- NAD

Local examination

In lithotomy position of patient, the findings observed were: patient had hairy perineal region with a small opening in right side of perianal region with no pus discharge through that opening, tenderness on touch with indurations was felt around external opening. Probing was done from external opening to access the internal opening but internally it was fibrosed. About 3 cm tract could be found during probing.

On proctoscopic examination no other anal pathology was seen. After complete examination the diagnosis was confirmed as Transsphincteric Fisula in Ano i.e. Bhagandara.

Perianal skin was normal with no dermatitis.

Laboratory Investigation: Blood and urine tests including bleeding time, clotting time, complete blood count, blood urea, fasting blood glucose, HIV, HbsAg.

Ksharsutra application- Pre-operative preparation

Local part preparation i.e., shaving was done. 5gm panchasakarchurna with Luke warm water was given to the patient at night before operation. Proctoglycerin enema was given at early morning on day of operation. After proper bowel passed, patient was taken to recovery room and injection T.T. 0.5ml IM was given and plain xylocaine 2% was given subcutaneously for sensitivity test.

Operative procedure

Patient was taken in lithotomy position on operation theatre table.

After proper painting and draping, local anesthesia with 2% xylocaine was infiltrated nearby opening and around anal verge after checking sensitivity test.

Assessment of extension of tract was done by probing. The track was of 6 c.m approximately. Probe was removed through anal opening via internal opening after threading of Ksharasutra into it and Ksharasutra was ligated appropriately. Then Apamarga Kshara vrana Basti 3ml was done inside the track. It was washed with distilled water 3 ml after 50 seconds. Check P/R was done to confirm the anal health. Complete hemostasis was gained and T bandaging was done.

Postoperative procedure

Ayurvedic medicines and sitz bath was given. Patient was admitted to the Hospital for 7 days till next Ksharasutra was changed and Vrana Basti was done for second time.

Oral medications

- Triphala guggulu 125mg TID
- Pancha tikta Ghrita Guggulu 125mg TID
- Kankayana Vati 125mg BD
- Abhyarishta 20ml with equal water BD
- Panchasakarchurna 3 grams with luke warm water at bed time.
- Avagaha swedan with Triphala kwath once daily.

Patient was advised to take Khichdi and Daliya during hospital stay. He was also advised to resume his normal day to

day activities.

Follow up

Patient was discharged from hospital after 1st Ksharasutra change and then asked for changing Ksharasutra every 7th day till cutting of the tract. Avadhya swedan and Jatyadi taila local application was asked to be done during this period. Patient was allowed to do his routine job after discharged from hospital. After 5 sitting the tract was totally cut and healing was achieved simultaneously. Jatyadi taila application on scar mark was advised.

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Complete cutting of the fistula track took place in 5 week. The Ksharasutra ligation and Kshara vrana Basti was applied successfully without any complications. It is a simple procedure where least instrumentations are required. It was seen that the track took less time to cut with the use of Kshara Nadi Vrana Basti.

DISCUSSION

Kshar is an alkaline substance obtained by methodological process of the ash of different Ayurvedic drugs. These Kshar are used as Anushastra- in place of sharp instruments having capacity of Chedan and Bhedana. Kshar is capable to cut tissue. It is capable to pacify the vitiated Doshas from the body. Kshar is considered to be superior among Shastra and Anushastra because it can be used when surgery is not possible is mentioned by Acharya Sushruta.

Sushruta described the treatment of Bhagandara as Bhesajja, Ksarakarma, Agnikarma and Shastra karma. In modern medicine treatment like fistulotomy, fistulectomy, seton ligation are indicated. These treatments have more recurrence rate and post-operative complications like hemorrhage, pain, and delayed healing etc. In comparison to modern treatment Ksharasutra ligation is better due to its minimal complications and less recurrence. Fecal incontinence and anal stricture are not seen in this cases of Kshara Sutra. The application of Ksharasutra is having anti- inflammatory and anti-microbial property and its alkaline property helps in cutting and healing. Cutting mainly occurs due to local action of Kshara, and the mechanical pressure of Ksharasutra knot. Haridra powder having antiseptic action helps in healing of the tract. Direct application of Kshara as Basti enhances its effect.

CONCLUSION

Bhagandara needs to be diagnosed early so that appropriate treatment can be given without delay. Ksharasutra helps to clean and cut the track and also prevent from infections. Ksharasutra at a time provides both cutting and healing, Kshar is also tridoshaghna so we can use it in any type of fistula tract. Postoperative complications using this technique is minimal. We have used Kshar Nadi Vrana Basti along with Kshar Sutra. It actually reduced the time period of cutting and gave faster healing. In an average Kshar Sutra cuts or heals the track by 0.5-1c.m in a week. Different Kshar sutra have different cutting rate. Apamarga Kshara sutra has approximately 1c.m cutting rate. But when Vrana basti was added to the treatment the cutting rate was faster. The Bhagandara was approximately 6 c.m long but it took 5 week to heal which is almost 1 week earlier. In this study a case report of Bhagandara treated by Apamarga Ksharasutra and Apamarga Kshara Nadi Vrana Basti was cured and no further complaints were found in the patient during follow up period.

So it can be concluded that Kshar Sutra is good treatment for Bhagandara but Ksharasutra combined with Kshar Nadi Vrana Basti is a better alternative which can be tried for faster healing. This was a single case study, more work can be done for statistical findings.

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